

Dichagyris chasmapsyche sp. n. from Tajikistan (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae)

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Abstract. Description of *Dichagyris chasmapsyche* sp. n. (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae), with 8 colour illustrations and 8 genitalia figures.

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Introduction

The latest publications on the Palaearctic taxa of the genus *Dichagyris* Lederer, 1867 were published by Varga, Ronkay & Ronkay 2020; Gyulai & Saldaitis 2021/a; Gyulai 2021/a; Gyulai & Saldaitis 2021/b; Gyulai 2021/b; Varga, Ronkay & Ronkay, 2021; Varga, Ronkay & Ronkay, 2023. In these communications, many new taxa were described from the high mountains of Asia, additionally three of them were species group revisions, as well. Here, the diagnosis and description of a new species is given, partly based upon of the expedition of D. Goshko to a rather unexplored area of Tajikistan.

The female genitalia of the new species and closely related taxa are figured below, even though the differences between them are mostly slight, as it is well known in this genus.

Abbreviations for personal and institutional collections used herein: HT = holotype; PT = paratype; PGM = collection of Péter Gyulai (Miskolc, Hungary); GYP = genitalia slide Péter Gyulai; BB = collection of Balázs Benedek (Mohács, Hungary).

Description of new taxa

Dichagyris chasmapsyche sp. n. (Figs 1–3, 9–11)

Holotype: female (Fig. 1), S.Tajikistan, South Ghissar mts.; Kulyab distr., Sari-Chashma, vill., South part of Hazretisho range, 1200 m, 22. V. 2023 leg. D. Goshko, slide no. GYP 5909 (coll. Péter Gyulai, Miskolc).

Paratypes: 4 females, with the same data as of the holotype; 3 females S.Tajikistan, South Ghissar mts.; Kulyab distr., Sari-Chashma, vill., South part of Hazretisho range, 1200 m, 17. V. 2023 leg. D. Goshko, slide nos. GYP 5907 and 5908 (coll. PGM); 5 females, from the same locality and collector, with the date 16-31. V. 2023. (BB).

Diagnosis. *Dichagyris chasmapsyche* sp. n. (Figs 1–3, 9–11) is an early flight species and only a series of females was found in the second half of May. Its flight period seems to be earlier than most of the taxa of the genus, with the exception of the taxa of the *Dichagyris forficula* species group and some species of the subgenus *Yigoga* Nye, 1975.

Without the knowledge of the male genitalia configuration, it cannot be associated with anyone of the *Dichagyris* species groups. In the external features, it resembles mostly *D. armeniaca* Kozhantshikov, 1930 (Figs 4, 12) (and its subspecies) and in the size and wing pattern also *D. ignara* (Staudinger, 1896) (Figs 5, 13), and *D. kongur* Varga, 1996 (Figs 6, 14), while *D. clara*

(Staudinger, 1888) (Figs 7, 15), (and its subspecies) and *D. celebrata* (Alpheraky, 1897) (Figs 8, 16), (and its subspecies) are less similar to the new species. The new species can be easily distinguished from all the above mentioned taxa by its whitish ground color of the forewings with scattered brown scales; the broad, whitish with light brown variegated cilia and the lighter, almost evenly pale brownish hindwings. This whitish-ochreous colouration of forewings occurs also in *D. armeniaca* (subsp. in Central Anatolia). However, the pattern of the new species is more contrasty than in *D. armeniaca*.

In the female genitalia configuration, the new species (Figs 9–11) reveals some unique features and is very easily distinguished from those of all the similar, closely related congeners mentioned above, by the much shorter ovipositor with angular, setose papillae anales; shorter apophyses anteriores and a. posteriores; by shorter, anteriorly broader, posteriorly much weaker ductus bursae and shorter but distally much broader appendix bursae. The female genitalia are mostly resembling to those of the *D. celebrata* species group (*D. celebrata*, *D. armeniaca*, *D. kongur*), but clearly differentiated by the essentially shorter and weakly sclerotised papillae anales. The male is unknown.

Description (Figs 1–3). Wingspan 28–34 mm, length of forewing 15–18 mm. The vesture of the body and ground color of the forewings evenly whitish with slight ochreous shade, and densely scattered with brownish scales. Orbicular and reniform stigmata as the ground colour, very finely black encircled; claviform stigma not present. The most conspicuous characters of the wing pattern: the big, blackish triangular subapical patch, the fine, black, zigzag antemedian line, the lacy, arched postmedian line and the fine, sinuous subterminal line, with a row of black wedge-shaped spots in the inner side. Cilia white and light brown variegated. Hindwings light brown with a long, faint, radial, slightly suffused stripe medially; much darker suffused in the marginal area; discal spot absent, cilia whitish. The underside of the wings very unical; the forewing whitish with faint light brown suffusion; submarginally with conspicuous, anteriorly broadened then evenly tapering ghost of the subterminal line; the marginal area white. Hindwing whitish with diffuse, slight brownish marginal suffusion.

Male genitalia. Unknown.

Female genitalia (Figs 9–11). Papillae anales weakly sclerotised, setose, angular; apophyses posteriores about twice as long as apophyses anteriores. The antrum finely sclerotized, U-shaped, the bilateral symmetrical extensions slight. Ductus bursae broadly tubular, anteriorly the broadest and longitudinally wrinkled, sclerotized, and more or less evenly weaker posteriorly. Appendix bursae large, rather short, more or less globular, distally much broaden; corpus bursae conspicuously longer, saccate.

Biology and distribution. The new species is known only from the type locality, near to rocky precipices, in medium altitude.

Etymology. *D. chasmapsyche* sp. n. is named from the combination „chasma“, which means rock precipice in C. Asia; „psyche“ is the ghost; its name means the soul of the rock precipice.

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Figures 1–8. Females of *Dichagyris* spp. adults. 1. *D. chasmapsyche* sp. n., HT, S.Tajikistan, S. Hissar, Sari-Chashma, GYP 5909 (PGM); 2. and 3. *D. chasmapsyche* sp. n., PT, S.Tajikistan, S. Hissar, Sari-Chashma (PGM); 4. *D. armeniaca* Kozhanchikov, 1930, Armenia, 15 km NE of Meghri, GYP 5912 (PGM); 5. *D. ignara* (Staudinger, 1896), China, Daban Shan, Xining (PGM); 6. *D. kongur* Varga, 1996, PT, Kazakhstan, Boguty Mts. (PGM); 7. *D. clara* (Staudinger, 1888), Kyrgyzstan, 5 km S. Enilchek, (PGM); 8. *D. celebrata* (Alpheraky, 1897), Iran, prov. Semnan, (PGM).

Figures 9–16. Female genitalia of *Dichagyris* spp. 9. *D. chasmapsyche* sp. n., HT, S.Tajikistan, S. Hissar, Sari-Chashma, GYP 5909 (PGM); 10. and 11. *D. chasmapsyche* sp. n., PT, S.Tajikistan, S. Hissar, Sari-Chashma, GYP 5907 and GYP 5908 (PGM); 12. *D. armeniaca* Kozhanchikov, 1930, Armenia, Meghri, GYP 5912 (PGM); 13. *D. ignara* (Staudinger, 1896), Mongolia, Bayanchongor aimak, Hangaj, GYP 5910 (PGM); 14. *D. kongur* Varga, 1996, PT, Kazakhstan, Tshundzha, GYP 5608 (PGM); 15. *D. clara* (Staudinger, 1888), Kyrgyzstan, 5 km S. Enilchek, GYP 5911 (PGM); 16. *D. celebrata* (Alpheraky, 1897), Turkmenistan, Kopet Dag, GYP 4080 (PGM).

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